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Changes in perceptions of ethical climate among undergraduate engineering students

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ABSTRACT

Promoting ethical conduct and social responsibility among undergraduate engineering graduates has been an ongoing challenge for many universities around the world. Among many factors shaping such commitments, the ethical climate within engineering degree programs specifically and universities more generally seems especially pertinent. Yet there remains a lack of research on, and understanding about, engineering students' perceptions of ethical climate, including how this changes over time and impacts their professional formation and values. This paper draws on an NSF-funded, mixed-methods, longitudinal research project conducted across four U.S. universities. The larger project aims to investigate perceptions and attitudes around ethics, social responsibility, and related concepts among engineering students. In this paper, we more specifically explore various facets of ethical climate across the three schools through a mixed-method explanatory study. We focus on quantitative survey measures (n=257) and qualitative interview data (n=33) collected from engineering students during their first and final years of college. We more specifically shed light on three main research objectives. First, we investigate how engineering students perceive ethical climate across the four universities. Second, we explore how students' perceptions of ethical climate change over time. Third, we look at how specific experiences may contribute to students' ethical climate perceptions, including changes over time. This study will appeal to engineering educators, policymakers and researchers who are interested in research on ethics, social responsibility, and related topics. By providing foundational insights about students' perceptions of ethical climate, we hope to inform strategies to improve the ethical climate at universities and ethical commitments of engineers.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Calls for developing ethical and socially responsible engineers have been persistent for many years among engineering educators and professional communities alike. Indeed, a recent revision of the ABET accreditation criteria for engineering degree programs requires as one of seven learning outcomes that graduates have “an ability to recognize ethical and professional responsibilities in engineering situations and make informed judgments, which must consider the impact of engineering solutions in global, economic, environmental, and societal contexts” [1]. Further, studies have shown that universities and engineering programs have a significant role in shaping students’ beliefs and norms related to engineering ethics [2, 3]. And, as universities continue to explore how to support such capabilities, promoting an ethical climate of conduct within and beyond the classroom would seem synergistic with this larger goal. Yet there remains a lack of research on, and understanding about, engineering students’ perceptions of ethical climate, including how this changes over time and more generally impacts their professional formation and values.

In response to this gap, this paper addresses the following research questions:

- RQ1. How do students perceive ethical climate and how do those perceptions change over time?
- RQ2. What experiences contribute to the shifts in ethical climate perceptions among students?

We additionally intend for our research findings to shed new light on possible connections between ethical climate, academic integrity, and professional conduct within engineering education and practice. We expect the research represented in this paper will benefit engineering educators, academic leaders and administrators, and professional organizations seeking to enhance the ethical climate in universities, and particularly in engineering programs. This work may also help stakeholders identify strategies for developing positive ethical behaviours among students.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Prior research has examined ethical climate in a variety of contexts. For instance, Finelli et al. hypothesized a conceptual framework for students’ ethical development during college that is comprised of three main parts: each student’s individual characteristics, the environment (including peer and organizational context), and the student’s specific experiences [4]. As these authors argued, these parts all work together to inform ethical development among students. Their conceptualization of the peer environment and organizational context included specific policies, values, practices, and beliefs of students, faculty, and administrators, which in turn seems to suggest that each institution has a unique ethical climate. Foundational research regarding ethical work climates was similarly conducted by Victor and Cullen [5]. They defined ethical work climates as “prevailing perceptions of typical organizational practices and procedures that have ethical content” (p. 101).

In order to better study and assess ethical climates, Arnaud developed a new measure based on Rest's four-component model [6,7]. The four components are moral judgment, moral sensitivity, moral motivation, and moral character, which are believed to underlie how people make ethical decisions. Arnaud built on Rest's model by proposing that these four components are not just present for individuals making decisions, but are also present for collective or social decision-making. She defined ethical work climates as "the shared, aggregate perceptions of employees with respect to the content and strength of the prevalent values, norms, attitudes, and behaviours of the members of a social system" (p. 348). Her model included six collective factors built on Rest's four individual components: collective sensitivity (moral awareness and empathetic concern), collective moral judgment (focus on self and focus on other), collective moral motivation, and collective moral character. Of these six collective factors, three have been shown to predict ethical behaviour: empathetic concern, moral motivation, and moral character. The present study adopts Arnaud's framework and uses a related survey tool to investigate perceptions of ethical climate among undergraduate engineering students.

3 METHODS

The larger project represented by this paper is a three-phased longitudinal mixed methods study conducted across four universities: Arizona State University, Brigham Young University, Colorado School of Mines, and Purdue University. The project aims to address three main research objectives, namely to: 1) Characterize patterns of ethical development among undergraduate engineering students during their four years of university education, 2) Identify specific context variables and types of interventions that impact student perceptions of ethics and social responsibility, and 3) Identify specific student characteristics that can be leveraged to grow programs oriented toward ethics and social responsibility.

To address these research objectives, qualitative and quantitative data were collected during three main project phases. The first phase data includes interviews and survey measures conducted during participants' first year of study (year 1). The second phase includes mid-point survey measures conducted in the fifth semester of study (beginning of year 3). The final phase includes repeat survey measures and interviews during participants' final semester (end of year 4). The survey includes various measures related to students' views on ethics and social responsibility, engineering ethics, justice beliefs, moral disengagement, ethical climate, etc. The semi-structured interview protocol also includes some prompts that revisit various questions and constructs drawn from the survey.

In this paper we focus primarily on data from phase 1 and phase 3 across three universities and related explicitly to the ethical climate construct. We have not included the fourth university in this paper due to a low response rate and small sample in the final round of data collection. The study follows an explanatory mixed method design approach, with the first phase involving quantitative analysis using

the survey data. For the quantitative phase, survey data from both year 1 and year 4 are used as data sources. The initial survey data administered in 2015 consists of 671 responses across three universities. This survey included eight scales, including the short form (19 items) of the Ethical Climate Index (ECI; [4]). These nineteen items measure six climate factors: norms of moral awareness, norms of empathetic concern, focus on self (reverse scored), focus on others, collective moral motivation (reverse scored), and collective moral character. Each item is measured on a six-point Likert scale ranging from completely false (1 point) to completely true (6 points). The higher the score on the ECI, the more students perceive their university's climate as ethical.

Because the ECI was being to measure the ethical climate of a university rather than a workplace, the wording of some items was changed to refer specifically to a university context. For example, the ECI item "People in my *department* recognize a moral dilemma right away" was changed to "People at my *university* recognize a moral dilemma right away." The survey was sent out in spring 2019 to the same group that completed it in 2015. In 2019, 266 students completed the survey for a response rate of 38%. Of those, 257 completed the ECI in both surveys. These 257 paired responses are the data analysed here. Internal reliability (α) for the nineteen-item ECI scale was calculated to be 0.907 for the initial survey and 0.921 for the final survey.

For the qualitative part of this study, interview data from year 1 and year 4 are used as data sources. In year 1 a total of 111 interviews were conducted. The interview prompts included a primary question asking students to describe the ethical climate at their university. This was followed by additional prompts including:

- a. What examples do you have that make you feel this way?
- b. Did you participate in any orientations sessions where expected behaviour was discussed?
- c. How were these expectations communicated to you?
- d. Does your university have a code of conduct that all students sign?
- e. How was this code of conduct presented to students?
- f. Have you discussed this code of conduct in any of your classes?
- g. Do you think students behave according to the code of conduct? Why or why not?
- h. Do you feel there are certain situations where you feel students are more willing to bend the rules? If so, when? And what makes you feel this way?

The repeat interviews were conducted again in 2019 with 33 students. The year 4 protocol included the same prompts as year 1 with an additional prompt probing students' perceived shifts in ethical climate perceptions during the interim period. The recorded interviews were further transcribed and cleaned for quality purposes. And, all student names in the interview transcripts were anonymized and correspond to the university affiliation based on first letter.

4 QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

As noted above, data from the 257 respondents who completed the ECI in both surveys are reported here. A paired-sample *t*-test showed that for the students who completed the ECI in both surveys, their overall ECI scores decreased by 3.8 points from 76.4 (standard deviation = 11.4) in 2015 to 72.6 (standard deviation = 12.4) in 2019 ($t = 5.063$, $df = 256$, $p < 0.001$).

When a split-plot ANOVA was used to see if there were differences among students at the three universities, the results showed that students at all three universities scored differently from each other ($F(2,254) = 18.025$, $p < .0001$, partial eta squared = 0.124). Post-hoc analysis showed that students at Brigham Young University had ECI scores that were statistically significantly higher than students at Colorado School of Mines and Purdue University at both time points ($p < 0.001$). The scores of students at Colorado School of Mines and Purdue University were not significantly different from each other in either 2015 or 2019 ($p = 0.459$) (Table 1, Fig. 1). There was no statistically significant interaction effect ($F(2,254) = 0.824$, $p = 0.440$) which means that students at all three universities changed at the same rate over time.

Table 1. Total ECI scores (standard deviations)

	2015	2019
BYU (n = 42)	85.2 (12.2)	79.5 (11.8)
Mines (n = 115)	73.5 (11.0)	70.6 (11.7)
Purdue (n = 100)	76.0 (9.7)	71.9 (12.4)

When examining the six individual factors using paired-sample *t*-tests, scores on five factors (norms of empathetic concern, focus on self, focus on others, collective moral motivation, and collective moral character) significantly decreased from the first to final measure (Table 2, Fig. 2). The one remaining factor (moral awareness) did not show a statistically significant change over four years ($p = 0.327$).

Table 2. Changes on ECI subscale scores (standard deviations), 2015 to 2019

	2015	2019	Change (2015 to 2019)	p-value
Focus on Self	7.4 (2.8)	7.0 (2.8)	0.4	0.044
Moral Motivation	9.7 (2.8)	9.1 (3.2)	0.6	0.001
Moral Awareness	13.8 (2.2)	13.6 (2.3)	0.2	0.327
Empathetic Concern	19.4 (3.0)	18.5 (3.2)	0.9	0.000
Focus on Others	13.3 (2.3)	12.2 (2.4)	1.1	0.000
Moral Character	12.8 (2.3)	12.2 (2.5)	0.6	0.001

Fig. 1 ECI scores for each university

Fig. 2 ECI subscale scores (overall)

5 QUALITATIVE RESULTS

Further analysis of the survey data corresponding to the subset of respondents (n=33) who completed interviews during year 1 and year 4 reveals that 22 of these individuals showed a decrease in ECI scores, 4 showed no change, and 7 showed an increase. This is quite consistent and representative of the larger survey data sample. Of these 33 pairs of interview data, 7 pairs were identified for further exploratory analysis. The 7 pairs selected represent respondents who either had the most significant decrease (n=4) or significant increase (n=3) on the ECI scales.

In the qualitative phase, these 7 pairs of interview data were further analysed using thematic analysis techniques [8]. Preliminary analysis of the interview data indicated that most students did not perceive significant shifts in their perceptions of institutional ethical climate from year 1 to year 4. The few that did acknowledge changes in their perception of the ethical climate did not characterize the change as positive or negative. Specifically, in response to the year 4 interview prompt asking students if they viewed any shifts in their ethical perception of their respective universities, most students stated that they did not perceive any major shifts.

For instance, Bagheera, who had one of the most substantial increases in ECI scores, stated in response to a question about whether he had experienced any shifts in perceptions of ethical climate over the last few years: “I’m not sure that it has much.” Similarly, Cody who had one of the largest decreases in ECI scores expressed uncertainty in her shifts in ethical climate perceptions as she responds by

saying “I mean, maybe a little bit.” In another account, Patricia, who also had a large decrease in ECI scores, states “I don't know if I would say more or less or if I could even pinpoint that. I just think it's changed.” Such responses indicate a lack of consistency between the ECI scores from the survey analysis and the interview data.

However, further review of the interview pairs suggests that although most students do not explicitly describe significant shifts in their perceptions of ethical climate or characterize it as negative or positive, their responses to ethical climate prompts in year 1 and year 4 reflect subtle changes in their views, which in turn could possibly explain the changes ECI survey scores. The following sections provide additional insights about how our subjects' comments may reveal shifts in ethical climate perceptions (decrease and increase) from year 1 to year 4, along with some factors that may be associated with these changes.

5.1 Experiences of students with large decreases in ECI Scores

Our findings suggest that for students with a large decrease in the ECI scores, their experiences of their academic community and competitive environment stand out as critical themes impacting their shifts in perceptions of ethical climate from year 1 to 4.

Sense of Community

In this section, we present findings from our data that illustrate how students' experiences of a sense of community – or the lack of thereof – may impact their views on ethical climate. For instance, Carly attests that there was a much better sense of community in year 1 as compared to year 4. She further adds that such a decline in the sense of community negatively impacts collaborations with her peers. Reflecting on a specific example demonstrating this type of shift, she explains:

I was living on a floor with 30 people, and everyone was so close together, like if you were working on something and you had a question you would just ask the person next to you. Versus like now, I live in a house with only six people, and none of them are civil engineers, so we're not taking any of the same classes. Yeah. There's not as much collaboration and stuff anymore like I do all my homework by myself.

As a further source of nuance, Carly further frames changes in ethical climate perceptions as she shifts from describing the ethical climate as being “very cooperative” in year 1 to “it's definitely cooperative like if you're already friends with someone” in year 4. Similar perceptions are also reflected in Cody's responses as he talks about a “cooperative” ethical climate in year 1 to “cooperative only among the people you know” in year 4. Such responses show how students' considerations of groups and experiences of community likely impact their views on ethical climate.

Competition

Our findings also suggest that students' changing experiences of competition shift their perceptions of climate during their undergraduate years. Not surprisingly, students with a large decrease in ECI scores often alluded to experiences of increasing competition in classes, job searches, etc. For example, both Cody and

Carly talk about witnessing increased cases of cheating on campus from year 1 to year 4. Cody even attributes this change to taking more difficult classes in the final years, explaining: “I’ve definitely been into some much more difficult classes where people are more willing to cut corners.” Braxton adds another layer of complexity in his comments about how competition negatively impacts ethical climate. Specifically, in his year 1 responses, Braxton talks about experiencing more competition and less cooperation academically, but he also emphasizes that the competition is often limited to the “smarter people” in classes where grades are curved. Yet in year 4 he shows signs of disappointment in the climate when he states that “people are slowly helping each other up, but if they help the other person up to above where they are, they try and cut them down.”

5.2 Experiences of students with large increases in ECI Scores

In contrast to the above themes, our findings suggest that for students with a significant increase in ECI scores, their experiences of cooperation among peers stand out as a significant theme contributing to their shifts in perceptions of ethical climate over time.

Collaboration and/or Cooperation

For interviewee subjects with a significant increase in ECI scores, we observe that their experiences of cooperation in their schools far exceeds the expectations they come in with. This could potentially help explain the increase in ECI scores for this subgroup. For example, as Chad states, “I thought coming into this school it would be cutthroat. That’s what I heard about this school just from high school in general. It’s a cutthroat school, and it will be tough. Not the experience I’ve had whatsoever.” He further contends that the cooperation he has seen among his peers and colleagues changed his views on ethical climate for the better. It is also interesting to note that another student, Bosco, also demonstrates subtle shifts in his perceptions of ethical climate. In year 1, he describes the ethical climate to be cooperative for the “most part” and notes that people don’t interact much in some classes, whereas in year 4 he talks about the ethical climate being “very cooperative.” He further states:

I see all the time there’s always students that are more than willing to help their friends or classmates with a difficult assignment that they understand. I think the proof of this is there’s the ... tutoring service where students volunteer to be tutors. There’s nothing [pause] they’re not getting paid or anything. They just want to tutor because they want to help other students out.

Other examples from all the three subgroup of interviewee subjects suggest that aspects of cooperation, as opposed to competition, are critical drivers of positive ethical climate perceptions among the participants in our study.

6 CONCLUSION

As noted above, our survey results suggest that a majority of our participants showed a decrease in ECI scores, meaning they had a less favourable view of ethical climate from year 1 to year 4. These results are also consistent with the views of authors such as Cech [2] who state that students’ sense of ethical responsibilities

and social consciousness tend to decline over the course of their engineering education. While preliminary qualitative analysis of responses to questions probing student perceptions of climate did not initially align well with our survey findings, through further review we observed some patterned themes among the participants that highlight specific shifts in perceptions from year 1 to year 4. More specifically, we find that experiences of competition and a perceived lack of community may contribute to negative shifts in ethical climate perceptions, whereas exposure to experiences of cooperation and collaboration likely improve such perceptions. Interestingly, through qualitative analysis, we also observe that in some cases subjects talk about using the community as a defence mechanism for dealing with negative ethical climate perceptions. Particularly, interview participants allude to forming groups to collectively navigate the broader institutional climate challenges, such as competition and the lack of a strong sense of community. These findings emphasize the need for educational institutions to rethink what kinds of experiences and environments they can provide students to promote more positive ethical climates.

However, one of the significant limitations of the study is that the qualitative phase included only interview data for students with extreme increase or decrease in ECI scores. We plan to revisit all 33 pairs of interview transcripts to identify emerging patterns of shifts in ethical climate perceptions across the universities. We also plan to further analyse data on ethical climate perceptions and changes based on institution type. Through these kinds of analyses, we hope to provide more detailed insights about how students perceive ethical climate at different universities.

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